

Building capacity for Open Science through training for institutional repositories

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Abstract

Apart from an underdeveloped infrastructure, a major obstacle to the implementation of the national Open Science (OS) Platform (adopted in 2018) in Serbia was the lack of institutionalized training for librarians and researchers. Training on OS was provided mainly through international projects. The Library and Information Science curriculum, professional development programmes for librarians, and training offered by university libraries were not focused on developing skills for OS.

When the University of Belgrade Computer Centre started building the repository infrastructure, this knowledge gap hindered the adoption of repositories and it was soon realized that the service package offered to institutions (software, hosting, technical support) should also include training, both for repository managers (usually librarians) and end users (researchers). To this end, a user support team was established. Two training modules and materials have been designed, and users have been offered a flexible training schedule. To address the knowledge gap, the training covers a range of topics beyond repository features and workflows: Open Access policies, FAIR principles, metadata standards, copyright, self-archiving policies, altmetrics, dissemination through metadata harvesting, discovery platforms (OpenAIRE, BASE, CORE), using institutional repositories in the context of Research Data Management and cultural heritage.

So far, this concept has proven to be efficient in mitigating the lack of institutionalized training. Along with supporting the growth of institutional repositories (more than 20 in three years), this approach to training has helped build an institutional capacity for OS, raise the awareness of librarians' roles, and increase employment opportunities for librarians. At the same time, it has stirred an interest in archiving research data and non-publication materials in institutional repositories, as well as a growing demand among researchers and librarians for additional, more specialized training, which can be easily provided by expanding the existing concept in a modular fashion.

Conference Themes

Interdisciplinary collaborations: Networks, services, methods

- Sharing best practices and knowledge

Training and skills for open science

- Sustaining open science training: people, resources, governance
- Skills within the wider research context

Keywords

repositories, training, skills, Open Science, librarians

Audience

repository managers, researchers, librarians, research communities

Lightning talk content

This talk presents a concept of Open Science-related training developed with the aim of facilitating the adoption of institutional repositories in a specific local context (Serbia). This context is marked by a considerable delay in infrastructure development, the lack of institutionalized training on Open Science, a knowledge gap, and insufficient library staff. Although institutionalized training is indispensable in the long-term, this example shows that a combination of bottom-up approaches and highly customized and informal training can increase the Open Science capacity of researchers, librarians and even institutions, which is highly relevant in the context of building competence and capabilities for EOSC. In these terms, it may be instructive for other environments with poor formal training on Open Science.

The adoption of the Open Science Platform (the national OS policy) in 2018, spurred the development of institutional repositories in Serbia and the leading role in this process has been taken by the University of Belgrade Computer Centre (RCUB). Before the adoption of the OS Platform, training on OS was mainly provided through international projects. The official Library and Information Science curriculum, professional development programmes for librarians and training programmes offered by university libraries did not address OS-related skills, due to which there was a knowledge gap in the library and research communities and this threatened the adoption of the developing infrastructure. Seeking to provide efficient training on institutional repositories, RCUB established a dedicated user support team responsible for designing and implementing training. The training programme covers a range of topics beyond repository features and workflows: Open Access policies, FAIR principles, metadata standards, copyright, self-archiving policies, altmetrics, dissemination through metadata harvesting, discovery platforms (OpenAIRE, BASE, CORE), using institutional repositories in the context of Research Data Management and cultural heritage. Training formats include predefined lectures and webinars, but also highly customized sessions and informal consultations.

As a result, dozens of repository managers (mainly librarians) and hundreds of end users (researchers) have been trained so far. A number of trained repository managers have already started organizing training on various OS topics at their institutions. Together with the user support team, they form a strong network enabling dynamic information exchange. At the same time, there is a growing interest among researchers for additional training on particular OS topics (RDM, copyright, integration of the repository in various institutional workflows). Also, continuous and flexible support encourages content diversity in repositories. The concept of training developed by the RCUB user support team has so far proven to be efficient in mitigating the lack of institutionalized training. However, in order to provide full support for all aspects of OS (esp. RDM and citizen science), it will be necessary to establish institutionalized training.

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